

**LANGUAGE UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK TO EXPRESS
"RESPECT" IN CLASSROOM AND EDUCATIONAL PROCESS**

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Annotation. Phraseological unities are characterized with the aid of using the semantic duality. One can't outline for positive the semantic that means of one after the other taken phraseological unities remoted from the context, due to the fact those word-combinations can be used as unfastened withinside the direct that means and as phraseological withinside the figurative that means. This article covers such language units in English and Uzbek that express "respect" in classroom and educational process.

Key words: language, contextual meaning, phraseological units, linguistic categories, education, semantics, respect.

Аннотация. Фразеологические единства характеризуются с помощью использования семантической двойственности. Нельзя выделить за положительное семантическое значение одного за другим взятых фразеологических единиц, удаленных от контекста, в связи с тем, что эти словосочетания могут употребляться как нескрепленные в прямом значении, так и как фразеологические в образном значении. В данной статье рассматриваются такие языковые единицы в английском и узбекском языках, которые выражают «уважение» на уроках и в учебном процессе.

Ключевые слова: язык, контекстуальное значение, фразеологизмы, языковые категории, образование, семантика, уважение.

Many young Uzbeks are trying to master the English language. Many Uzbek students enroll in English language courses at many universities in the capital, Tashkent. For many, English is a break from the past and represents a new future. For young men, English is a natural step in their business career. As one male student stated, "English will help me build strong business relationships and make my business richer." For many of the female students I spoke to, they see English as a pathway to a professional career in translation or to higher education. Uzbeks take education seriously thus many of them apply for master's and doctoral degrees. For many students, both within the capital and in the regions, learning English is a stepping stone to higher education in the US and Europe. Previously, studying outside Uzbekistan was reserved for the elite, but now many universities offer English language courses, allowing Uzbek students of all economic levels to study abroad in English-speaking countries. They want to learn. One of the advantages of wanting to learn English for Western countries is that Uzbek students can study in Western countries by learning English, then return to Uzbekistan and bring Western ideas with them. will be able to bring. This will continue to further develop their country and achieve a more "open" policy. After the collapse of the Soviet Union and until the early 2000s, the Uzbek government financed undergraduate and graduate studies of Uzbek students in foreign countries (eg, the United States) through the Umid program.

At the end of this program, the graduates had to return to Uzbekistan, and most of them work in the government. This program allowed Western-educated students to influence the policies and procedures of the Uzbek government. Unfortunately, this program ended in the early 2000s when relations with the West began to deteriorate.

Today, there is a scholarship for master's students in Uzbekistan through the Karimov Foundation. After graduation, students are also required to return to

Uzbekistan, but there is no requirement to work in the government. Although some students have started working for the government, there is not enough data or personal testimony to understand the effects. However, any Western-educated Uzbek will undoubtedly bring back some ideas to help the country in its efforts to build democracy. Among the linguistic categories that can be observed in most of the world's languages, we can see categories that have a common typological feature, but can be expressed in different ways in different languages. Studying these language facts, identifying their similarities and differences is of great importance for literary scholars, especially for graduates of language faculties of higher educational institutions who want to become English language teachers and translators in the near future.

Many studies have been conducted to explain the difficulty of acquiring EP for the Uzbek people, and most of them have focused on the phonological differences between English and Uzbek. Therefore, this study seeks to explore the goals and challenges of students and teachers in learning and teaching EP. Ultimately, this study hopes to shed light on elements of EP that facilitate learning and teaching methods in kindergartens. My personal teaching experience and observations are the strong motivation for this research. Everything I learned in my English teaching career came from my Uzbek English teachers, and my EP is no exception. In my early years of teaching, I rarely used English to explain to my students because I thought my EP was not good enough. After many years, I began to use English more often and felt more comfortable and confident in speaking with my students of all ages from all parts of Uzbekistan, although I still have something I knew it needed improvement. Because of my long time learning and using English, I knew that this important change had happened to me. The grammatical center of such units is the verb, and the semantic center is the nominal component in most cases: to fall in love. In some units, the verb is both grammatically and semantically central: not knowing

the ropes. These units can also be perfectly idiomatic: burn a boat, vote with your feet, take to the cleaners, etc.

There are three principles of classification of phraseological units. The most famous is the synchronic (semantic) classification of phraseological units by V.V. Vinogradov. He developed some of the ideas first put forward by the Swiss linguist Charles Bally and gave a strong impetus to a purely lexicological treatment of the material. So, phraseological units are defined as lexical complexes with specific semantic properties and classified accordingly. Its classification is based on the motivation of unity, which is the relationship between the meaning of the whole and the meanings of its components.

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